

AI-Powered Content Moderation: A Secure Approach to Digital Communication

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Abstract - Safeguarding the digital world from the use of technology itself has become one of the most major stark challenges for the users. AI-enabled content moderation is typically achieved through the use of Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), and Natural Language Processing (NLP) in detection and filtration of inappropriate contents from textual messages as well as images. It is on the application of AMR-CNN for the detection of text-based toxic contents and Faster R-CNN for image-based violent content detection that this discussion revolves around. Built on top of a social platform by Flutter and Firebase, the system enables real-time message and post moderation. The research describes CNN-based image analysis, NLP based text classification, and highly efficacy in establishing safer digital interactions.

Keywords: Content Moderation, AMR-CNN, Faster R-CNN, Real-time Filtering, Deep Learning, Flutter, Firebase, Text Moderation, Image Moderation.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

Moderation on online communication platforms have limiting Factors containing toxic messages, violent images etc. Manual review is time and revenue consuming in traditional moderation approaches. AI powered moderation is able to deal with this systematically using Deep Learning/NLP for instance in order to remove dangerous content.

B. Problem Statement

- Recognizing harmful messages/wisdom in chat, without getting normal conversations impacted
- Identifying crude images (violence, weapon, explicit) in the posts of user

- Developing real-time filtering on a social media-style platform

C. Objectives

- Employ AMR-CNN for detecting text-based toxicity
- The Faster R-CNN would be integrated for classification to undesirable images.
- Guarantee real-time moderation with the help of Firebase & flutter

D. Challenges in AI-Powered Content Moderation

For text and images AI-based moderation, is not that simple (compared to the general content moderation systems). Toxic text detection is context/slang/implicit harmful intent understanding of NLP traditional models often just not built to handle, this is much harder. The binary, content based moderation (violent or nudity detection) likewise needs fine-grained classification with a low false positive/false negative rate as it would not be very useful to flag perfectly good content. Thus further validating the difficulty in training given the lack of labeled datasets for specific content categories.

E. Need for Context-Aware Moderation

Rule-based filtering by the most traditional moderation systems do not go deep into the user-generated content context. While text moderation is usually hard with sarcasm, domain-sensitive toxicity and multilingual nuances a deep learning-based NLP will be required. With image moderation, the real challenge is to demarcate between violence (contextual such as educational or news images) and harmful imagery Faster R-CNN based models are trying to solve. Adding with real-time moderation of AI into digital platforms is allowing freedom to use with the consideration of safe communication environment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Overview of Content Moderation

AI-supported moderation is becoming popular because it is able to fast large-scale data analysis. CNN-derived models are some of the most accurate for image classification (studies) and NLP models such as AMR-CNN detect toxic speech well.

B. Related Work

- AMR-CNN— Extracting the meaning from beyond words for accurate toxic message detection (classification).
- Faster R-CNN: Beats traditional CNNs at detecting certain objects in images which makes it a perfect candidate for violent content detection. *C. Research Gap*
- The current systems have no real time filtering, are unautomated and oftentimes wrong. This research fills this gap by introducing automation through AI based system in an actual application.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. The system is divided into:

- Text Moderation: Analyzes the content of the message to detect toxic words and AMR- CNN.
- Image Moderation: Input any image to detect if inappropriate content by using Faster R-CNN.
- Backend Processing with Firebase ML Kit for real-time execution of the AI model.

B. Technologies Used

- Machine Learning Framework: TensorFlow, PyTorch.
- Deep Learning Models: AMR-CNN (for text), Faster R-CNN (for images).
- NLP: Tokenization, Sentiment Analysis
- Tools for Development: Flutter (Front-end), Firebase(Back-end).

C. System Architecture

1. Flutter Frontend – Provides an intuitive UI for content sharing, messaging, and notifications.
2. Firebase Backend – Handles user in authentication, content storage, and message routing.
3. Machine Learning Models –

- AMR-CNN for toxic text detection
- Faster R-CNN for violent image recognition

4. Cloud Firestore – Stores user-generated contents along with the moderation logs.

D. AI-Based Content Moderation: Model Training and Implementation.

To improve content moderation in Prueba platform we implemented an AI-based detection models with text and image. The system combines AMR-CNN for malicious text detection and Faster R-CNN for detecting images that are harmful. Dataset of toxic messages and inappropriate images were getting trained in our dataset which was cobbled together from a publicly available and customized.

Here training aspect Parameters:

1. Text Model (AMR-CNN)

- Base Model: AMR-CNN
- Training Data: 50,000 labeled toxic and non-toxic messages
- Batch Size: 32
- Optimizer: Adam with dynamic learning rate
- Accuracy Achieved: 82.4%

2. Image Model (Faster R-CNN)

- Base Model: Faster R-CNN with ResNet Backbone
- Training Data: 10,000 images (violent, explicit, and safe images)
- Batch Size: 16
- Optimizer: SGD with momentum
- mAP (Mean Average Precision): 87.6%

Using Firebase Functions and TensorFlow as backend, the models were deployed on the Prueba social platform. The mechanism runs realtime message/image scanning before pushing them to the platform.

Results and Implementation model did work to restrict the bad content and we keep safer online community. Below are some of the flagged examples:

- Inappropriate Image Detection (Figure 1): A post was flagged due to the containing inappropriate visual elements.

- Toxic Message Detection (Figure 2): A message containing harmful language that was detected and blocked in real-time.

Figure 1: Flagged Toxic Message

Figure 2: Detected Inappropriate Image

E. System Deployment and Model Integration

Now AI driven content moderation systems incorporate AMR-CNN to detect toxic text content and Faster R-CNN for violent/image that are not acceptable. The social platform is flutter-and Firebase-powered to guarantee real-time content moderation in minutes.

Workflow:

- A message/image enters on a platform as the Text message/Image submitted by the user.
- The system sends the input to corresponding deep learn models:

- Uses AMR-CNN [18], a pre-trained toxic text dataset trained on text to detect toxic language, cyberbullying, or hate speech..
- Explain Faster R-CNN annotations on images, both detecting violent content or unsuitable or inappropriate images from an image moderation set.
- Purposefully flagged as inappropriate, the mechanism being let through consists of:
 - Warns the user and prevents submission,
 - Requests manual review by an admin, or
 - Removes the content automatically.
- Only after labeling as appropriate, the content is approved and viewable on the platform. It enables real-time moderation with high accuracy, making the social interactions a little more digital safe.

F. Code Snippet: AI-Based Content Moderation in Flutter & Firebase

1. Text Moderation using AMR-CNN (Python - Firebase Function)

This function takes in text messages, passes them through a pre-trained AMR-CNN model for processing and also filters out inappropriate content.

```
import firebase_admin
from firebase_admin import firestore
import torch
from amr_cnn_model import AMRCNN # Load your pre-trained model
from text_preprocessing import preprocess_text # Custom function for preprocessing

# Initialize Firebase
firebase_admin.initialize_app()
db = firestore.client()

# Load AMR-CNN model
model = AMRCNN()
model.load_state_dict(torch.load("amr_cnn_model.pth"))
model.eval()

def moderate_text_message(doc_id, message):
    processed_text = preprocess_text(message)
    prediction = model(processed_text) # Get toxicity score

    if prediction >= 0.7: # Threshold for toxic content
        db.collection("messages").document(doc_id).update({"status": "flagged"})
        return "Inappropriate message detected"
    else:
```

```
db.collection("messages").document(doc_id).update({"status":
"approved"})
return "Message approved"
```

2. Image Moderation using Faster R-CNN (Python Firebase Function)

This function scans an uploaded image, detects inappropriate content using Faster R-CNN, and flags it.

```
import torchvision.transforms as transforms
from PIL import Image
from faster_rcnn_model import FasterRCNN # Load your
trained model

# Load Faster R-CNN model
model = FasterRCNN()
model.load_state_dict(torch.load("faster_rcnn_model.pth"))
model.eval()
```

```
def moderate_image(image_path):
    image = Image.open(image_path).convert("RGB")
    transform = transforms.Compose([transforms.ToTensor()])
    image_tensor = transform(image).unsqueeze(0)

    # Get predictions
    predictions = model(image_tensor)

    # Check for inappropriate content (based on detection
    confidence)
    for pred in predictions[0]["scores"]:
        if pred > 0.8: # Confidence threshold for inappropriate
        content
            return "Inappropriate image detected"

    return "Image approved"
```

3. Flutter Code to Send Data for Moderation

This Dart function in Flutter sends text messages and images to Firebase for real-time moderation.

```
import 'package:cloud_firestore/cloud_firestore.dart';
import 'package:firebase_storage/firebase_storage.dart';

Future<void> submitMessage(String message) async {
    final docRef =
    FirebaseFirestore.instance.collection("messages").doc();

    await docRef.set({
        "message": message,
        "status": "pending",
        "timestamp": FieldValue.serverTimestamp()
    });

    print("Message submitted for moderation.");
```

```
}

Future<void> submitImage(String filePath) async {
    final storageRef =
    FirebaseStorage.instance.ref().child("uploads/${DateTime.now()}
    .jpg");
    await storageRef.putFile(File(filePath));

    final imageUrl = await storageRef.getDownloadURL();
    await FirebaseFirestore.instance.collection("images").add({
        "imageUrl": imageUrl,
        "status": "pending",
        "timestamp": FieldValue.serverTimestamp()
    });

    print("Image uploaded for moderation.");
}
```

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Performance Metrics

- Text Model (AMR-CNN): Achieved an F1-score of 82.4% in detecting toxic content.
- Image Model (Faster R-CNN): Detected violent content with mAP (mean Average Precision) of 87.6%.

B. System Testing

- Unit Testing: Verified correct classification of toxic words and images.
- Integration Testing: Ensured smooth workflow between the AI models and Firebase.

C. Comparison with Existing Systems

Feature	Manual Moderation	AI-Based (Proposed System)
Speed	Slow	Real-Time
Accuracy	Inconsistent	High Text model (82.4% F1-score)
Accuracy	Inconsistent	High Image model (87.6% F1-score)
Scalability	Not scalable	Fully scalable

TABLE I. TABLE TYPE STYLES.

D. IMPLEMENTATION

1. Training the AI Models

- Dataset for Text Analysis: Labeled Toxic messages for the AMR-CNN.
- Image Dataset Set for Faster R-CNN training: The collection of violent/non-violent images
- Training: Supervised learning using loss functions on accuracy for trained models.

2. Integration with Flutter & Firebase

- Flutter UI: Displays flagged messages and images.
- Firebase ML Kit: Processes incoming messages and images in real-time.
- Cloud Firestore: Stores user data and moderation logs.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Prueba, the proposed system aimed at improving content moderation by AI driven digital communication security. AMR-RNN for toxic text detection and Faster R-CNN for violent image detecting module combined to guarantee a safe respectful online space from college-centric social platform.

A. Content Moderation Process

1. Text-Based Moderation

- AMR-CNN for analysis of messages sent on platform to detect already predefined toxic key words, possessives as well harmful phrases while messaging.
- The model reads the text, detects toxicity and then passes on message to deliver you the content filtered message..

2. Image-Based Moderation

- When users upload images, Faster R-CNN scans for violent or inappropriate content.
- If detected, the system either blocks the upload or flags it for further review by the admin.

3. Real-Time Processing

- Firebase ML Kit enables seamless and real-time AI model execution for both text and image moderation.
- The integration with Flutter ensures instant user feedback, preventing the spread of inappropriate content.

Figure 3: Flow Chart.1

B. System Workflow

The following flowchart gives a clear insight into the user interaction with content moderation in Prueba platform. It shows the AMR-CNN and Faster R-CNN based text image analysis in each step of analyzing content to make sure unwanted content is filtered right before publishing.

The chart grabs every necessary piece from unfiltered content submission to processed kind of AI-backed moderation and decision seamlessly integrated. With real-time filtering techniques, the system improves user security and ensures a safe digital communication.

C. Performance Evaluation of AMR-CNN and Faster R-CNN in general-purpose AI models

We evaluate the output of our content moderation system with a performance-analysis of AMR-CNN on toxic text detection and Faster R-CNN for violent image detection. These models were trained on a dataset, created specifically for the task of on-the-fly moderation so that this is the content they are trained too.

Some of the most salient observations were that in order to detect subtle toxic aspects of text and the violent elements of images, particularly when using models that have not be fine-tuned for specific moderation tasks was problematic. In comparison, well-trained models on our dataset proved to be more precision improved in detecting inappropriate content and more suitable in real world applications.

The convention here is that of general-purpose in AI performance means models are not sector-specific and designed to take on different tasks. These text and image models (such as GPT-4o, general vision) can have the ability to process but are not necessarily designed for specific tasks like toxic content detection or violent imagery.

Your solution is a domain-specific, dataset-trained model. Superior to AMR-CNN and Faster R-CNN that are specifically tuned for content moderation using curated dataset, resulting in a much higher accuracy in terms of finding harmful content as compared to an uninformed AI model.

D. Evaluation Metrics for AMR-CNN and Faster R-CNN in general-purpose AI models

To validate the performance of our system, standard evaluation metrics such as Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-Score for text classification were used, along with mAP (Mean Average Precision) for image detection.

- AMR-CNN achieved an accuracy of 82.4% in detecting toxic text, highlighting its effectiveness in filtering harmful content.

- Faster R-CNN demonstrated an mAP of 87.6% in recognizing violent imagery, significantly improving detection rates compared to generic moderation approaches.

The results evidence the need for content moderation systems to use specialized, dataset-trained models that outperform traditional alternatives with respect to accuracy and efficiency. In this version, Models are framed as specialized solutions trained on dedicated datasets as opposed to general-purpose AI models, making it clear without compromising interpretation.

B. Comparison with GPT-4o: Enhanced Performance in Content Moderation

We compared our AI-powered content moderation systems against the base GPT-4o model as part of the study to assess the modules capabilities. The second main objective was to evaluate the performance of AMR-CNN and Faster R-CNN in detecting toxic text and inappropriate images as compared to a generic model such as the base GPT-4o.

A significant finding was involving the real-time moderation that general trades very well in general NLP but really missed the cuts on a lot of subtle toxic content within text as well as violent elements in images too. Our system used AMR-CNN for toxic text filtering and Faster R-CNN for detection of violent images and proved great in terms of accuracy and precision for flagging any inappropriate content.

E. Evaluation Metrics for AMR-CNN and Faster R-CNN in Comparison with GPT-4o.

To additionally verify the performance of our system, we evaluated output with common evaluation metrics for text classification (Accuracy, Precision, Recall F1-Score) and mAP (Mean Average Precision) on the image detection task.

We present the results in Figure 4, AMR-CNN surpassed detection accuracy 82.4% on toxic text which was an improvement over GPT-4o with 76.2% suggesting again an ease with which AMR-CNN could be trained given accurate annotations. One similarly obtained an mAP of 87.6% in identifying violent imagery with Faster R-CNN, while GPT-4o generic vision model could barely do anmAP in 70.1%. That calls to mind and underlines how effective our fine-tuned models are at identifying/filtering harmful content.

V. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion & Future scope

This study achieved the successful deployment of AI content moderation in real time on social networking platforms. The two-model approach (AMR-CNN for text, Faster R-CNN for images) provides a high degree of accuracy and automation for filtering inappropriate content.

B. Future Enhancements

- GPT-based NLP models for the better context understanding in messages.
- Hybrid AI models combining image and text analysis for improved moderation.

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